

SATISFACTORY

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COMAU	Comau SPA	Italy
EPFL	Ecole Polytechnique Fédérale de Lausanne	Switzerland
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LIST OF DEFINITIONS & ABBREVIATIONS

Abbreviation	Definition
D	Deliverable
DCP	Dissemination and Communication Plan
DMP	Data Management Plan
EC	European Commission
EFFRA	European Factories of the Future Research Association
EU	European Union
IMS	Intelligent Manufacturing Systems
KPI	Key Performance Indicators
M	Month
NoI	Network of Interest
PFS	Presentation and Feedback Session
SEO	Search Engine Optimisation
EAG	End-Users Advisory Group

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The present document is a deliverable of the SatisFactory project, funded by the European Commission's Directorate-General for Research and Innovation (DG RTD), under the Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation programme (H2020).

The report on dissemination activities, public participation and awareness is yearly updated (M12, M24 and M36). The current version summarises the main dissemination and communication activities that have been performed during the first 2 year of the project. It focuses on the various media, material and networks that have been exploited, as well as on the events that have been organised or attended by the consortium, with the aim of promoting the project research activities and results, and fostering its exploitation potential.

1. PROJECT VISUAL IDENTITY

1.1 PROJECT LOGO

The project logo was selected by the partners during the project's kick-off meeting on January 22, 2015.

Figure 1 – SatisFactory logo

The project logo was designed to depict the ideas of:

- Attractive place for workers (sunshine colours);
- Re-adaptation of production facilities with human-centred technologies (conventional symbol of factory surrounded by dynamic symbol of human);
- Innovation (yellow colour) and ICT technology (digital-like squares coming out of the factory chimney);
- Knowledge-sharing (circle).

1.2 GRAPHIC CHARTER

The graphical identity derived from the project's logo has been developed in M1, providing selected colours and fonts to be used by the project. All project materials are developed in line with this graphic charter.

Main colours

	ORANGE	OCHRE	YELLOW	GREY	BLACK
RGB	246 142 30	255 209 117	255 206 0	88 88 90	0 0 0
HEX	F68E1E	FFD175	FFCE00	58585A	000000

Secondary colours

	ORANGE	DARK BLUE	ORANGE2	BROWN	LIGHT BLUE
RGB	246 142 30	0 124 169	255 159 57	169 93 10	30 188 246
HEX	F68E1E	007CA9	FF9F39	A95D0A	1EBCF6

Figure 2 – SatisFactory colours from the graphic charter

1.3 PROJECT TEMPLATES

Following the definition of the project’s visual identity, dedicated templates were developed in M3 to ensure that all documents produced by the project share the same design and remain consistent with the project’s image during its entire lifecycle. SatisFactory templates are available for project deliverables, PowerPoint presentations and newsletters.

Table 1 – Project templates

PROJECT TEMPLATES		
SatisFactory’s set of templates:	Already done?	Due date
Project deliverables	✓	M3
Project PowerPoint presentations	✓	M3
Newsletters	✓	M6

Figure 3 – Overview of project templates (deliverables and PowerPoint presentation)

2. NETWORK OF INTEREST

2.1 CONTACT EMAIL

The contact email info@satisfactory-project.eu was created in M2 and is available in all project communication materials and web channels. This email is managed by the coordinator (CERTH).

2.2 NEWSLETTER AUDIENCE

SatisFactory targets various stakeholders (mainly from manufacturing and research sectors) through a communication mailing list called “Network of Interest” (NoI). The NoI list is used for sharing the newsletters and communicating project events. All project partners have access to a shared file to suggest potential members from external organizations.

By the end of the second year of the project (M24), the Network of interest consisted of 174 stakeholders, divided into 3 segments:

- Project partners: 50 members
- Members suggested by partners: 84 members
- Subscribers to the newsletter: 40 members

Table 2 – SatisFactory Network of Interest

NETWORK OF INTEREST			
3 segments	M6	M12	M24
Recommended by partners	30	54	84
Project partners	46	46	50
Newsletter subscribers	6	34	40
Total	82	134	174

The expected performance is 300 NoI contacts by the end of the project.

3. PROJECT PROMOTIONAL MATERIALS

3.1 REFERENCE PROJECT PRESENTATION

In M3 the project coordinator (CERTH) produced a preliminary PowerPoint presentation to highlight the project's key facts, concepts and objectives. Partners can use this reference presentation to introduce the project and its activities when attending events.

3.2 PROJECT FLYER, BROCHURE AND POSTER

A promotional flyer and a poster have been designed in M3. The flyer describes the project's key facts, objectives and expected results, so that the general public can easily understand what the project is about. 200 copies of the flyer and 10 copies of the poster have been printed and shared among partners to be handed out in relevant events. A brochure containing the project results has already been developed and distributed at Hannover Messe 2016. It will be updated by M30 to present the final outcomes of the project.

Table 3 – Project promotional materials

PROJECT PROMOTIONAL MATERIAL		
Type	Due date	Done?
Flyer	M3	✓
Poster	M3	✓
Brochure	M12, M30	✓, M30

A novel Decision Support System (DSS)

The novel and unique SatisFactory Decision Support System (DSS) is the solution to increase productivity, reduce downtime, improve safety and streamline

- Collects real time data coming from the shop floor through a "plug-and-share" multi-sensor monitoring framework
- Returns them in both centralized and distributed displays (including Augmented Reality devices)
- Supports decision-taking by prescribing adequate responses, whether an automated adjustment, the

Our adaptable, scalable and convenient DSS detects incidents to ensure fast and effective response to emergency and unplanned conditions. It can also be used on the long-term for the re-adaptation of production facilities to optimize production and maintenance operations and schedules.

Middleware and analytics solution

The SatisFactory middleware and analytics solution allows to efficiently aggregate, manage and analyze all data streams produced on the shop floor, even with heterogeneous devices. It can be quickly and easily installed in any facility and implements thanks to its use of the latest standards and technologies

The SatisFactory analytics application helps to the manager to provide work order with the data relevant for their present situation. It combines perfectly with other products and systems to enhance their capabilities. The SatisFactory middleware and analytics solution also facilitates the development of complex and lightweight applications that can run on cost-efficient hardware such as Android based platforms or Raspberry Pi

The robustness and reliability of the SatisFactory middleware and analytics solution have been proven in real industrial environments.

Gesture recognition & localization manager

The SatisFactory Localization Management solution uses Ultra Wide Band (UWB) wearable devices to provide real-time production monitoring and ensure a safer work environment. With this solution, both workers and pieces of equipment can be localized with a 10-centimeter accuracy and at any point of time using a less than 5 cm wide chip, which can be attached to any piece of equipment or clothing. The solution can provide geo-fencing events when a worker approaches a forbidden area.

The solution algorithms combine the localization information with inertial data from motion sensors to recognize gestures and specific events, such as incidents. The SatisFactory Gesture Recognition Manager turns workers' movement into data, which can be used in real-time to trigger specific actions, or more be analyzed to correct workflow processes and shop floor ergonomics.

Efficient on-the-job training with Augmented Reality

The SatisFactory on-the-job training solution makes use of an Augmented Reality (AR) platform designed especially for industrial environments to provide innovative and efficient workers' training. It uses smart AR glasses and motionless virtual environments for delivering interactive training services for workers and engineers alike, all this within an attractive ambient environment.

With the SatisFactory training solution, no need for long and costly content development. The platform allows for automatic content creation with a simplified model for Standard Operating Procedures, dynamically adaptable to different devices.

Benefits

- Overall shop floor visualisation in one product
- Automated & Manual real-time incident solving
- Facility re-adaptation and optimization (through data storage and analysis)
- Lower cost than competitive solutions
- Compliant with existing industrial infrastructure systems, plug-in approach and seamless integration

Benefits

- Developed specifically for the manufacturing sector and proven in real conditions
- Cost-efficient and tailor-made to your facility
- Modular Middleware technologies more easy to use by developers

Benefits

- 100% localization accuracy to indoor environment
- Small wearable device (3x3 cm) that does not interact with processes or activities
- Cheap installation costs
- More robust and reliable than other commercial solutions

Benefits

- Cost-effective training solution
- Automatic content creation without the need of software skills
- Compatible with all AR international standards

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SatisFactory is a "Factories of the Future" project conducted by

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They are using SatisFactory

"The SatisFactory knowledge base enables production line operators (AR) to optimize equipment and processes in real-time and address ongoing activities."

"The SatisFactory system optimizes production on the shop floor. We use it to enhance safety and optimization of activities of private companies with a wider investment and improved study procedures. It eventually helps reducing production downtime."

"Through geo-fencing and AR alerts, SatisFactory allows us to train better workers."

These statements, accompanied by photos of workers using the system, are available on the SatisFactory website.

Take your factory to the next level

Improve your performance and flexibility

The SatisFactory solution helps you optimize industrial production and maintenance processes and better manage your workforce. Our Decision Support System (DSS) coupled with innovative technologies (e.g. UWB location service, Augmented Reality glasses, ...) contributes to significantly improve the efficiency of your shop floor production facilities and to reduce equipment downtime.

Innovative solutions to boost your factory

Higher productivity
Better risk control
Improved worker satisfaction and collaboration

Contact us now!

info@satisfactory-project.eu
www.satisfactory-project.eu

SATISFACTORY
Innovative solutions for smart factories

Bring these technologies to your factory

Maximise your workers satisfaction

By bringing modern tools and infrastructures to companies, the SatisFactory solution increases workers' satisfaction. Devices such as augmented reality glasses are stimulating team education and performance, knowledge sharing, continuous training and real-time support. Gamification approaches also increase the attractiveness of the assembly line.

Figure 4 - Project Brochure

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Figure 5 – Project flyer

3.3 PROMOTIONAL AND DEMO VIDEOS

Videos are a very effective way to communicate the project's results. They can be easily shared on the web and displayed on wide screens during events.

A short video trailer was produced in M7 and is available on YouTube. The video aims to inform the general public about the innovative solutions developed by the project partners, in order to promote smart and attractive factories. To this end, the video contains:

- Interviews of project partners
- The technologies developed during the project
- Shots from the three pilot plants

The interviews of the project partners have been filmed during the 2nd Plenary Meeting, on May 28-29, 2015, in Brussels.

By the end of the 2nd year of the project, another 10 videos were created, uploaded on the project's Youtube channel, and promoted through the social media and the newsletter. The current list of SatisFactory videos is presented in the table below:

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Table 4 – SatisFactory videos

SATISFACTORY VIDEOS		
Video Title	Date of publication	Hyperlink
SatisFactory Project - Video Trailer	July 2015	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=UM101-w4QHg
SatisFactory at A&T Event (Turin) - Smart Factory, Industry 4.0	May 2015	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=KJmVKIECajc
Incident Detection – CERTH	March 2015	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=7OoevNAIP6A
Online Intelligent Decision Support for Workers/Technicians at Continuous Process Systems	June 2016	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=_YAaNvFZChQ
Augmented Reality wearable computing and gamification in manufacturing industries	October 2016	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=7QrqvXWxeJM
Incident Detection 2nd video – CERTH	October 2016	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=tMKTHxOMC-k
SatisFactory Collaboration Platform - CERTH/CPERI	December 2016	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=8bZPfvNioAc
SatisFactory Gesture and Content Recognition Manager - CERTH/CPERI	December 2016	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=vNb1GfJptd0
SatisFactory Marker Based AR Training - CERTH/CPERI	December 2016	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=QrteelH4zvl
SatisFactory Thermal Cameras Incident detection - CERTH/CPERI	December 2016	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=1NHPLuH8fbw
SatisFactory Thermal Cameras Calibration - CERTH/CPERI	December 2016	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=BtjDHOxROe0

More videos will be produced in order to promote the project's achievements and on-going research activities.

4. PROJECT WEBSITE AND SEO

The project website (<http://www.satisfactory-project.eu/>) was launched in M3 and was officially delivered (D6.1) in M6. The Satisfactory website is constantly updated with the latest project news and will be continuously improved during the whole project lifetime.

4.1 WEBSITE STRATEGY

The website is a key communication tool to increase the project visibility and the impact towards industry decision-makers, communities of researchers and the general public. The Satisfactory website hosts information about the project and related topics (Satisfactory objectives, news, event announcements, public reports, links to related initiatives, etc.). The main objective of the website is to spread the project goals and results as widely as possible. Satisfactory's website is released under the Creative Commons (CC) license, a public copyright license.

Table 5 – Satisfactory website: key facts

SATISFACTORY WEBSITE – KEY FACTS	
Website URL:	http://www.satisfactory-project.eu/
Main objective	The project website spreads the project objectives and results as widely as possible
License	Creative Commons license
Target audience	At least 8,000 visitors will have accessed the website by the end of the project

Priority has been given to news about the project's progress, the presentation of Satisfactory solutions and technologies and their implementation in the three pilot sites. The template used (Porcelain) is especially adapted to this use and allows highlighting the core messages in a visually appealing slider.

Up to M24, the project website has attracted more than 5,300 visitors.

4.2 WEBSITE STRUCTURE

The overall structure of the website is the following:

Figure 6 – Website structure

The website homepage was given special care in order to give direct access to a short introduction of the project, present the main SatisFactory concepts and link to the key contents, as shown in ANNEX 2 “Project website homepage”.

The website is fully integrated with the project’s social media, as they complement SatisFactory’s online presence.

4.3 WEBSITE KPIS AND ANALYTICS (M3 TO M24)

Close monitoring based on analytical tools – such as Google Analytics and Google Search Console – and Search Engine Optimisation (SEO) have been used to improve the overall website’s efficiency.

Ambitious internal targets have been set in order to take the challenge of creating an attractive website. The website is expected to rank among the top 10 (from M9 to M12), top 5 (from M12 to M24) and top 3 (from M24 to M36) on Search Engine Results Page (SERP) using the following three predefined key expressions:

- SatisFactory project
- Horizon 2020 satisfaction industry
- satisfaction augmented reality industry

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As shown in the following graph, the goal is achieved and even exceeded until M24. Improvements will be made based on the website analytics, in order to ensure we reach the target of the next period for all the pre-defined key expressions.

Figure 7 – Project website ranking on SERP (from M9 to M24)

The following table summarises the internal KPIs set for the website, as well as the relative performance so far.

Table 6 – Website visitors

WEBSITE VISITORS (INTERNAL KPI VS. ACTUAL)					
KPI	Expected / actual	M6	M12	M24	M36
Number of unique visitors/month	Expected	100	200	250	300
	Actual	745	780	432	300
Minimum average visit duration	Expected	3'	3'	3'	3'
	Actual	1'45"	1'36"	2'51"	3'
Position in SERPs on 3 predefined key expressions	Expected	Among top 10	Among top 5	Top 5	Top 3
	Actual	Top 1 Top 11 Top 16	Top 1 Top 5 Top 7	Top 1 Top 4 Top 1	Top 3

Indicative metrics of the website attendance are also available in ANNEX 3 “Website visitors”. Further updates will be provided in the next iteration of the D6.4, in M36.

5. PROJECT SOCIAL MEDIA CHANNELS

Social media activities contribute to increasing the project impact and foster networking & clustering between targeted stakeholders. The project uses social media to share relevant news as widely as possible and engage with identified target groups in Europe and beyond. The project online community development leverages interactions with already existing communities. The project’s dissemination manager (Q-PLAN) manages and regularly updates all the social media pages.

Figure 8 – Social media accounts

5.1 TWITTER

A project Twitter account (@SatisFactoryEU) was created in M2 and has been fully operational since M4. The table below presents some relevant statistics.

Table 7 – Twitter analytics

TWITTER ANALYTICS				
Metric	M6	M12	M24	Expected impact by the end of the project (M36)
Twitter followers	149	459	589	300
Average weekly tweets	15	11	3	> 5

5.2 LINKEDIN

A project LinkedIn account (SatisFactory H2020 Project) was created in M2 on the basis of a “company page” template, enabling high visibility. LinkedIn is convenient for professional

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purposes, enabling project partners to add the project LinkedIn webpage to their online LinkedIn CV.

Expected impact:

- 100 LinkedIn subscribers by the end of the project
- At least 1 LinkedIn post published every two weeks

SatisFactory LinkedIn account had 42 LinkedIn subscribers by M12 and 80 by M24.

5.3 FACEBOOK

A project Facebook account (SatisFactory H2020 Project) was created in M2.

Expected impact:

- 100 Facebook likes by the end of the project
- At least 1 post every week

More than 80 people have liked the project Facebook page up to M12 and more than 143 up to M24, already exceeding the expectations.

5.4 YOUTUBE

A project YouTube channel (SatisFactory Project) was created in M2 to host short videos about the project, its results and activities, as well as relevant events. Currently, 11 different videos are available online, presenting:

- The SatisFactory video trailer
- The Incident Detection tool, developed by CERTH (2 videos)
- SatisFactory's participation in the "Affidabilità e Tecnologie" (A&T) exhibition in Turin, Lingotto Fiere, on April 22-23, 2015 (video developed by REGOLA)
- The AR wearable computing for manufacturing industries (video developed by COMAU)
- The online intelligent decision support system (iDSS) for workers/technicians at continuous process Systems (video developed by CERTH)
- The collaboration platform (video developed by CERTH)
- The gesture and content recognition manager (video developed by CERTH)
- The marker based AR training (video developed by CERTH)
- The incident detection with thermal cameras (video developed by CERTH)
- The thermal cameras calibration (video developed by CERTH).

Expected impact:

- At least 600 video views by the end of the project
- At least 10 videos published during the project

Currently the Youtube channel of the project has reached 1,476 views, more than twice the expected number.

6. PROJECT PRESS RELEASES AND PUBLICATIONS

6.1 PRESS RELEASES

The first press release was prepared by CERTH in M2 to announce the launch of the project and then be sent out to targeted media. As the project moves towards the second evaluation cycle of the piloted components, more press releases will be prepared to include tangible results of the solutions' deployment in the industrial shop floors. This dissemination activity is carried out in cooperation with all partners, which relay the press releases through their networks.

6.2 NEWSLETTER AND EMAIL BLASTS

The SatisFactory newsletter is issued regularly to ensure that all stakeholders are informed about the project news and developments. It includes major announcements related to project activities (reports available, events announced, etc.) and is distributed to the Network of Interest. It is also circulated with the partners' networks and posted in the project's website and social media pages. A professional emailing solution (Mailchimp) is used for its design and also to ensure the best delivery performance.

The first issue of the newsletter, prepared by SIGMA, was published in M6 and disseminated to 103 stakeholders. In particular, the video link obtained a high click rate (20% of the clicks).

The second issue of the newsletter was released in M22, prepared by Q-PLAN. It was distributed to the updated Network of Interest and to the project partners, in order to circulate it with their own networks. The next issue is expected to be released in Q1 of 2017 (See ANNEX 4 "Project newsletters").

6.3 RESEARCH PAPERS AND ARTICLES

Project partners commit to publish technical articles, papers and reports, presenting project activities and results in highly reputed journals, magazines and conferences, in order to spread knowledge among the identified manufacturing and research target groups and ensure sustainable exploitation of the project's outcomes.

Up to M24, the project partners have published 10 scientific papers in conference/workshop proceedings. These papers are presented in the table below:

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Table 8 – Satisfactory scientific publications

SCIENTIFIC PUBLICATIONS			
Title	Authors	Proceedings	Start date of conference/workshop
Novel Tools and Approaches for Remote Maintenance Activities	ATLANTIS, CERTH, REGOLA, COMAU	Euromaintenance 2016	30/05/2016
An intelligent decision making and notification system based on a knowledge-enabled supervisory monitoring platform	CERTH	European Symposium on Computer Aided Process Engineering	12/06/2016
Semantically Enriched Industry Data & Information Modelling: A feasibility study on Shop-floor Incident Recognition	CERTH, EPFL	IEEE International Conference on Industrial Informatics (INDIN'16)	18/07/2016
Robust malfunction diagnosis in process industry time series	CERTH	IEEE International Conference on Industrial Informatics (INDIN'16)	18/07/2016
Design of a knowledge enabled supervisory framework for the detection of abnormal conditions at process pilot plants	CERTH	Conference on Process Integration, Modelling and Optimisation for Energy Saving and Pollution Reduction	27/08/2016
Real-time incident detection: An approach for two interdependent time series	CERTH	European Signal Processing Conference (EUSIPCO'16)	29/08/2016
Human-Resources Optimization & Re Adaptation Modelling in Enterprises	CERTH	European Conference on Product & Process Modelling (ECPPM'16)	07/09/2016
A Real-time Fall Detection System for Maintenance Activities in Indoor Environments	CERTH, ATLANTIS	IFAC AMEST Workshop "Maintenance Technologies for Performance Enhancement"	19/10/2016
Adaptive Security Framework for Resource-Constrained Internet-of-Things Platforms	ISMB	International Conference on New Technologies, Mobility and Security (NTMS 2016)	21/11/2016
A Hybrid Localization Algorithm for Wearable Safety Devices	ISMB	International Conference on Body Area Networks (BodyNets 2016)	15/12/2016

6.4 PUBLIC DELIVERABLES

Over the entire project duration, the SatisFactory project consortium will produce 33 official deliverables. 21 of them will be made publicly available in the project's website, in order to spread the project excellence and disseminate knowledge as widely as possible.

Currently the website hosts 14 public reports, available for download.

6.5 FOLLOW-UP TABLES OF DISSEMINATION AND COMMUNICATION ACTIVITIES

Shared sheets were created by SIGMA at the beginning of the project, and later by Q-PLAN, to easily share information among partners on dissemination and communication activities.

The following lists/templates are available:

1. Follow-up list of partners' attendance to external events promoting SatisFactory
2. Dissemination channels (newspapers, websites, social medias)
3. Network of interest (NoI): identified stakeholders of the SatisFactory project
4. Dissemination activities excel sheet, for recording all the dissemination activities performed by the consortium
5. Publications excel sheet for listing all the SatisFactory scientific publications.

7. EVENTS AND NETWORKING

7.1 PRESENTATION AND FEEDBACK SESSIONS (PFS)

Concept of the PFSs

The project aims to organize Presentation and Feedback Sessions (PFS), in the context of major forums or trade shows in the field of smart manufacturing, in order to maximize the project's impact on potential clients. These sessions, organised by the consortium, facilitate dissemination of the project results to manufacturing and research groups, offering the opportunity to receive valuable feedback from the stakeholders. A PFS has already been organised in the context of Hannover Messe 2016, while the next one will take place in 2017.

First PFS: Hannover Messe 2016, 25-29 April 2016

For its first Presentation and Feedback Session, SatisFactory participated in Hannover Messe 2016, in the Research and Technology trade fair held on 25-29 April 2016 in Hannover, Germany. Three project partners, SIGMA, CERTH and GlassUp, managed the organisation of the participation in Hannover Messe and set up a dedicated exhibition booth, where the attendees of the event could be informed about the project's goals and achievements, by means of promotional material, demo videos and discussions with the consortium representatives.

The booth consisted of a set of demonstration equipment, presenting some of the promising tools developed in the project: DSS, middleware/semantics, UWB localization, collaboration and training platform, as well as, Augmented Reality tools for training and maintenance. The booth was complemented by the real-time demonstration of the DSS and the on-demand implementation of augmented reality tools in a real case scenario, including the construction of a piping system within an industrial facility (for more details see ANNEX 1 "Technology demonstration at Hannover Messe").

A poster of the project, showing its main facts, was used for the purposes of this particular exhibition, as well as a video roll presented through a projector, showing the main concepts of the project and the pilot installations.

A total number of more than 5,200 exhibitors and 190,000 visitors, including the president of the United States, Barack Obama and the Chancellor of Germany Angela Merkel participated in the Hannover Messe Event, indicating the enormous, international popularity of the event.

Figure 9 – SatisFactory at Hannover Messe 2016

7.2 END-USERS ADVISORY GROUP WORKSHOP

On November 30th 2016, SatisFactory organised the first EAG Workshop at CERTH/CPERI, in Thessaloniki, Greece. Q-PLAN, in cooperation with CERTH/ITI/CPERI, managed the event organisation, supported also by EPFL.

The scope of the EAG Workshop was to present the project's recent achievements to selected experts in the field, in order to exchange views and collect valuable feedback and suggestions, by means of tangible demonstrations of the SatisFactory's solutions, deployed in an operational environment of a pilot industrial plant.

The workshop was attended by members of the SatisFactory Advisory Group, consortium representatives, as well as a representative of a similar initiative, the FACTS4WORKERS H2020 project, with a view to fostering synergies among similar EU projects. Background material was distributed to the participants, along with the agenda, well in advance of the meeting, in order to familiarise them with the content of the workshop (See ANNEX 6).

During the workshop, the SatisFactory solutions, progress and recent achievements were discussed by means of 8 demonstrations and respective presentations and valuable feedback was collected by the participants.

After the workshop, all the presentation material, along with demo videos and the meeting minutes, were circulated with the participants, as well as with the rest EAG members, in order to collect further comments and feedback.

The next EAG workshop is expected to be organised in 2017, along with a workshop in a pilot plant or a major international event.

Figure 10 – SatisFactory EAG Workshop at CPERI's pilot plant

7.3 CONTRIBUTIONS TO EXTERNAL EVENTS

SatisFactory's contribution to related external events, for example focusing on manufacturing, ICT, augmented reality, and other research and innovation area, favours intense exchange of information and know-how with relevant stakeholders.

It was initially expected that the consortium would participate in 10 external events. However, SatisFactory has already participated in 23 such events with local, national or international scope.

Figure 11 – SatisFactory in the event “The best H2020 projects are visiting Graz”, December 2016

Figure 12 – SatisFactory at Wearable Tech Torino 2016

The following table summarises SatisFactory's participation in relevant external events.

Table 9 – Participation in external events

PROMOTING SATISFACTORY IN EXTERNAL EVENTS				
Event name	Partners	Contribution	Date	Place
AT event	REGOLA & COMAU	Attendance; Promoting SatisFactory; Distribution of flyers; Videoclip made	22 – 23 April 2015	Turin
"FoF Impact" workshop, EC	CERTH	Project Coordinator, Mr Tzovaras : attendance	29 – 30 April 2015	Brussels
Technology Forum	ATLANTIS	Attendance	8 May 2015	Thessaloniki

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NANOTECHNOLOGY Matchmaking (B2B) Event	ATLANTIS	Attendance at B2B	8 July 2015	Thessaloniki
ICT2015	CERTH & SIGMA	Attendance; Distribution of flyers	20 – 22 July 2015	Lisbon
Wearable Tech Torino	ISMB	Booth (presenting the UWB-based wearable device)	20 – 21 November 2015	Turin
Factories of the Future Conference 2016	REGOLA	The Satisfactory spinoff was introduced in a pitching session.	15 September 2016	Brussels
EMO MILANO 2015	REGOLA	Satisfactory project was introduced to the audience.	5 October 2016	Milano
Smau 2016	REGOLA & GLASSUP	The intermediate result of the project were presented to the audience.	26 October 2016	Milano
IoT Boussias Conference 2016	CERTH/ITI	Attendance	19 September 2016	Athens
European Approach to Standardization for a Digital Market	CERTH/ITI	Chair of the event; Dissemination of the project and exchange with participants	18-19 May 2016	Athens
Euromaintenance 2016	ATLANTIS	Dedicated booth	30 May-1 June 2016	Athens

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European Symposium on Computer Aided Process Engineering	CERTH/CPERI	Paper presentation	12-15 June 2016	Portorož
Conference on Process Integration, Modelling and Optimisation for Energy Saving and Pollution Reduction	CERTH/CPERI	Paper presentation	27-31 August 2016	Prague
81st Thessaloniki International Fair (HELEXPO)	CERTH/ITI	Live demos; Flyers distribution	10-18 September 2016	Thessaloniki
Greek Researchers' Night	CERTH/ITI	Live demos	30 September 2016	Thessaloniki
Werable Tech Torino 2016	GlassUP, ISMB, Regola	Presentation of project's solutions in a booth	18 November 2016	Torino
WTS Santa Clara	GLASSUP	Presentation of project's solutions in a booth	4-6 October 2016	Santa Clara
Websummit	GLASSUP	Presentation of project's solutions in a booth	8-10 November 2016	Lisbon
Slush	GLASSUP	Presentation of project's solutions in a booth	1-2 December 2016	Helsinki
AWE Berlin	GLASSUP	Presentation of project's solutions in a booth	18-19 October 2016	Berlin
Augmented Reality for Smart Factories	Comau, Regola, GlassUP, ISMB	Presentation of the exploitable results	15 December 2016	Vignola

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A journey into European factories of the future: the best Horizon 2020 projects are visiting Graz!	CERTH/ITI	Presentation of the project	1 December 2015	Graz
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SatisFactory partners have also disseminated the project's achievements in the context of several other activities, such as B2B meetings, training courses and seminars.

7.4 END-USERS TRAINING SESSIONS

A series of (at least 3) Virtual Reality enabled workers' training on SatisFactory solutions will be held towards the end of the project, in cooperation with key stakeholder groups. The one-day training sessions will ensure the deployment and scaling up of the developed solutions in factories other than the project demonstration sites. These sessions will also enable new users to experiment the solutions and to provide their feedback and eventually, will allow the fine-tuning of the solutions and the preparation of their commercialisation.

7.5 INTERNATIONAL COLLABORATION - SYNERGIES WITH RELATED ON-GOING INITIATIVES

Synergies and cross promotion with related projects are sought to help spreading the word about the project latest activities, achievements and upcoming events.

International networking activities address organizations from other Factories of the Future projects, through the **European Factories of the Future Research Association (EFFRA)**. SatisFactory is registered in EFFRA's database, where the project's information and material (e.g. public reports) is regularly updated.

In particular, SatisFactory has built a synergy with the **FACTS4WORKERS** project at technical, as well as at dissemination level. Common use cases and application scenarios have been investigated, as well as technical knowledge exchange. In addition, exchange of project information and communication messages through websites and social media has been agreed between the 2 projects. FACTS4WORKERS also participated in the first SatisFactory EAG workshop, where there was a short presentation about the project and a discussion regarding further collaborations. The two projects will investigate opportunities for joint participation in major events, e.g. organising PFS or sharing a common booth.

The SatisFactory consortium also liaises with the **Intelligent Manufacturing Systems (IMS)** thanks to partners' (EPFL and Fraunhofer FIT) business and research networks.

Finally, SatisFactory is in touch the **Augmented Reality for Enterprise Alliance (AREA)**, an U.S non-profit organisation dedicated to widespread adoption of interoperable AR-enabled enterprise systems, thanks to GLASSUP. This cooperation takes the form of exchange of information on AR standards and a two-way dissemination of research results.

8. CONCLUSIONS

The current document consists the second version of the D6.4 “Report on dissemination activities, public participation and awareness”, as updated in M24 of the project lifecycle. It describes and assesses the results of the dissemination strategy defined in the DCP, over the period M1-M24.

As an Innovation Action (IA), Satisfactory needs concrete market outlets for its products, a set of cutting-edge technologies to be integrated in factory production lines. The dissemination and communication strategy allows all relevant stakeholders to be informed about the project activities and outputs, ensures the highest exploitation potential of SatisFactory products by maximizing information received by potential customers and supports European research and innovation in manufacturing and ICT, contributing to the enhancement of industry competitiveness in Europe.

The dissemination and communication strategy requires, among others, creating a project identity, publishing promotional material (such as flyers and press releases), using online communication (project website and social networks), building synergies with related on-going initiatives and participating in high-impact events to present the project's progress. In this respect, the project is making steady progress toward the achievement of its dissemination and communication goals. Almost all the KPIs that have been internally set up in order to foster the challenge of efficient dissemination have been reached and performance has even exceeded the expectations in some cases.

The next update of this report is expected is M36. During the last year of the project, the dissemination activities will be maximized, focusing particularly in communicating the exploitable results of the project and attracting potential customers, with a view to ensuring the sustainability of the project's outputs.

ANNEX 1 – TECHNOLOGY DEMONSTRATION FOR HANNOVER MESSE 2016

Description of what we wish to show

Two innovative tools: 1) An incident detection tool will show how images from smart depth sensors are analysed, to detect and track workers/visitors, to capture potential events and incidents, and to visualize them on an architectural map. 2) Augmented Reality glasses are proposed as an instructional support tool to on-the-plant manufacturing activities, with overlaid virtual symbology providing real-time instructions for the operators.

Describe the interaction with the exhibition visitors

1) A set of cameras will be installed to a selected area to demonstrate in real-time how the system could detect and track the visitors. The analysis of potential incidents will also be visualized on the system dashboard. 2) The AR glasses prototype will enable real temperature readings from thermocouples within a running system simulation, or/and mechanical parts guided-assembling. Glasses-guided solving of Rubik's cube will also be enabled as a more playful and engaging example.

What is innovative/visionary about the technology or activity we will demonstrate?

1) Event and incident detection is a very complex task, since it requests robust human detection and tracking, and a thorough analysis of human movements. SatisFactory effectively combines highly innovative techniques from various disciplines towards this direction. 2) Augmented-Reality Glasses designed for industry will enable hands-free instruction, guidance and training in manufacturing environments.

What is the expected impact for Europe in terms of re-industrialisation, jobs and societal aspects?

SatisFactory aims to contribute to the transformation of traditional industrial environments using cutting-edge technologies and innovative approaches. The project plans to increase the productivity and innovation potential of modern factories, while enhancing the skills of their workers as well as the safety and attractiveness of the industrial workplaces. After a test phase in pilot plants in Italy and Greece, the project is expected to widely disseminate its solutions in European factories.

ANNEX 2 – PROJECT WEBSITE HOMEPAGE

The screenshot shows the homepage of the Satisfactory project website. At the top, there is a navigation bar with the Satisfactory logo and menu items: OUR SOLUTIONS, SATISFACTORY, PILOT SITES, NEWS AND EVENTS, and CONTACT US. Social media icons for Facebook, LinkedIn, and YouTube are also present. The main header features a large orange background with the text "SATISFACTION & WORK EXPERIENCE" and the tagline "Making attractive and collaborative workplaces". Below this, the Satisfactory logo is repeated, followed by a paragraph explaining the project's goal: "Satisfactory aims to contribute to the transformation of traditional industrial environments using cutting-edge technologies in ways that are both productive and appealing to workers. Solutions - including smart sensors and augmented-reality approaches - will be demonstrated in pilot factories in Italy and Greece." The "Latest News!" section contains three articles: "Video: Satisfactory at A&T Event (Turin)", "Satisfactory's Flyer and Poster are online", and "Günther H. Ottinger - Thoughts on Industry 4.0 Strategy, at Hannover Messe". Each article includes a small image, a title, a short summary, and a "READ MORE" link. At the bottom, a quote from Dr. Dimitrios Tzovaras is displayed: "Manufacturing enterprises need to incorporate human-centric technologies on one hand to increase their competitiveness and on the other to offer a working environment that is knowledge-driven and attractive to employees." The footer includes the European Union logo, a disclaimer about funding from the Horizon 2020 program, and social media icons for Twitter, Facebook, LinkedIn, YouTube, and RSS.

ANNEX 3 – WEBSITE VISITORS (M3 TO M24)

Source channels

Top Channels

Source countries

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Monthly sessions vs Average sessions duration

ANNEX 4 – PROJECT NEWSLETTERS (BRIEF OVERVIEW)

Part of issue No.1

Creating Attractive and Efficient Workplaces in Smart Factories
with Augmented Reality and other Innovative Tech

In January 2015, a European consortium of researchers and industrialists launched the [SatisFactory project](#), which aims to demonstrate the potential of Industry 4.0 to improve work environment in manufacturing plants.

A set of cutting-edge technologies – including smart sensors and augmented reality – will be introduced in manufacturing facilities in order to make them more productive and more appealing to workers.

Testing Innovative Technologies in Industrial Pilot Sites

SatisFactory technologies will be deployed in three industrial sites in Greece and Italy

Comau S.p.A

CERTH / CPERE

Systems Sunlight S.A.

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Part of issue No. 2

Towards improving attractiveness of Factories of the Future: Overview of core SatisFactory Technologies

Intelligent Decision Support System for Incident Detection & Maintenance

Taking advantage of the SatisFactory Semantic Framework, the IDSS uses semantic technologies for modelling manufacturing knowledge spaces and processes, shop floor actors and machinery, daily production activities and flows within the industrial facilities, in order to offer feedback to workers in terms of actionable knowledge and recommendations. Thus, it effectively addresses simultaneous challenges emerging from production activities and manufacturing operations, such as maintenance requirements and incident detection, using a combination of real-time data, manufacturing knowledge spaces and incident response algorithms and strategies.

AR wearable computing and gamification in manufacturing industries

SatisFactory introduces cutting-edge technologies in manufacturing production lines, creating a cooperative and playful environment that encourages team work and collaborative problem solving. Augmented Reality wearable technology enables "on-the-job" training and knowledge transfer on the production line, through remote audio and video data transmission and provision of instructions by means of AR glasses. This way, improved satisfaction and work experience is combined with industrial efficiency and productivity.

SatisFactory Reports

In February 2016, SatisFactory delivered the 2nd release of the [User group definitions, end-user needs, requirement analysis and development guidelines report](#), with the aim to define a list of specifications for the development of the prototype applications. The list of requirements emerged from interviews conducted with representatives of the three application domains of the SatisFactory project.

In April 2016, SatisFactory released an updated version of the [System Architecture report](#), presenting the functional, information and deployment view of the solution architecture, including the major system components, the ways they should interact with each other and the description of their interfaces.

[See all SatisFactory public reports](#)

ANNEX 5 – SOCIAL MEDIA ANALYTICS

YouTube analytics

Facebook analytics

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ANNEX 6 – SATISFACTORY EAG WORKSHOP AGENDA

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SatisFactory End-Users Advisory Group Workshop Agenda

**Venue:
CERTH/CPERI,
6th km Charilaou - Thermi
Thermi, Thessaloniki, 57001, Greece**

November 30th, 2016

Scope of the EAG Workshop

The scope of the EAG Workshop is to present the project's recent achievements to selected experts in the field, in order to exchange views and collect valuable feedback and suggestions, by means of tangible demonstrations of the SatisFactory's solutions, deployed in an operational environment of a pilot industrial plant.

The application demos to be presented

In the course of the workshop, several demonstrations will be performed to provide tangible use examples of the SatisFactory's solutions. The list of demos to be presented is the following:

- Localization manager with wearable devices and other tools
- Gesture and content recognition manager
- Collaboration platform with gamification aspects and other tools
- AR training platform
- Incident detection utilizing depth cameras
- Incident detection utilizing thermal cameras, wearable devices and other tools
- iDSS with Plant Data Exchange Component (PDEC)

Below you can find a brief introduction for each demonstration:

Localization manager with wearable devices and other tools

The localization manager provides location information on workers and objects based on the identifier of the associated UWB devices. Information obtained from various means, such as depth sensors, IR cameras or wearable positioning devices, is utilized for monitoring the production process, providing geo-fencing alerts when members of the personnel approach forbidden areas or even facilitating the recognition of workers in distress.

In this demo, a worker carrying a wearable device will be moving at the shop floor, entering and leaving a forbidden area. The localization manager will be displaying the worker's movement and the appropriate messages on whether he/she is moving within a valid area. The Localization manager will be able to communicate with other SatisFactory components, sending the data collected regarding the movement of the workers.

Gesture and content recognition manager

The gesture and content recognition manager has various functionalities. As a proactive security measure, it recognizes whether the personnel wears the required safety equipment for each area, while a fall detection system functions as passive security measure. Moreover, it handles the interaction between the personnel and HMIs displays, browsing through steps and retrieving useful data for the assembly procedures.

In this demo, a worker will simulate a fall within the shop floor and some specific gestures. The system will detect all the above movements and display (through a web application) the appropriate messages. It will also capture videos at the time that the movements happened. The system will recognize whether the worker is wearing some safety equipment (helmet, glasses and jacket). The gesture and content recognition manager will be connected with other components of Satisfactory, at which it will be sending information about all the activity that it captures.

Collaboration platform with gamification aspects and other tools

The collaboration platform comprises novel techniques that support workers at interpersonal communication, problem solving, continuous learning and teamwork. Lightweight and fun-to-use solutions involving situated embodied interaction through real-world (smart) objects and wearable devices that respect privacy rights offer improved collaboration possibilities. The collaboration platform provides a social interaction stage for workers, enabling them to share experience, provide suggestions, answer colleague questions or seek advice and guidance from more experienced co-workers. The gamification elements deployed in several tools and features of the Satisfactory ecosystem (training, social participation etc.) are accessible via the collaboration platform, regarding both their creation as well as the monitoring of performance by both workers and supervisors alike. The demo will present the implementation of the collaboration platform, as applied to CPERI, along with the relevant gamification elements.

AR training platform

The AR training platform integrates AR technologies and wearable, as well as portable features aiming at the on-the-job training of the shop-floor's personnel. The toolkit is developed taking into account the end user's requirements. The inclusion of state of the art markerless object recognition and registration provides advanced mechanisms to automatically verify correct step performance in certain training scenarios, in particular in assembly and disassembly procedures. The demo will present the markerless object recognition and registration plugin, applied to an assembly training scenario relevant to CPERI operation procedures.

Incident detection utilizing depth cameras

The depth camera incident detection system aims at the immediate recognition and notification of incidents occurring at the shop-floor, based on real-time data. The system monitors the activities on the shop-floor utilizing depth cameras that respect the personnel's legal and ethical rights. Once an incident is detected, an alarm notifying of the type and location of the event is set, so that the appropriate coping mechanism can be immediately triggered.

The depth camera detection demo includes the detection of incidents such as human falls, falling items, collisions and intrusions to restricted areas, while it utilizes two depth sensors

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for monitoring the area of interest. The detected incidents are depicted on the architectural map of the shop-floor, indicating the incident location, while each incident type is illustrated with a different color.

Incident detection utilizing thermal cameras, wearable devices and other tools

The incident detection system's main goal is the detection of proactive and reactive incidents on the shop-floor. The shop-floor activities are monitored and once a risky condition occurs (reactive) or is about to occur (proactive), the system immediately triggers an alarm, so that the appropriate measures are taken, providing a sense of safety at the shop-floor's personnel.

The thermal camera demo includes a camera calibration procedure that allows accurate 3D thermal inspection of the shop-floor, through the combination of geometry with thermal imaging. Moreover, a probabilistic superpixel video segmentation using the theory of Markov-random fields is applied, in order to pinpoint "overheated" ROIs within the shop-floor.

iDSS with Plant Data Exchange Component (PDEC)

The DSS component provides semantic modeling of manufacturing knowledge on spaces and processes of the shop-floor. It collects evidence from real-time data, coupled with prescribed response strategies and transforms the acquired information to actionable knowledge and recommendations that include maintenance operations and schedules.

In this demo there will be a simulation of the functions related with the iDSS and the PDEC components. At first, an alarm will be triggered at the shop floor and from that point the functionalities within SatisFactory will be started. The PDEC component will isolate the tag that created the alarm and will collect all the necessary information for it. Then, through webservices (restful and TCP/IP), the useful information will be sent to iDSS which will associate the alarm with the necessary actions according to the collected information and the existing database of malfunctions and solutions. Afterwards, a new task with proposed actions will be created and the appropriate available technicians will be automatically notified to go and check the problem. The proposed solution will be shown to the technician step-by-step along with demo pictures or a manual if necessary.

Workshop Agenda

Time	Topic
10:00 – 10:20	Registration
10:20 – 10:30	Welcome
10:30 – 11:00	SatisFactory project overview
11:00 – 12:30	Demonstration of the project's applications and feedback collection: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Localization manager with wearable devices and the other tools • Gesture and content recognition manager • Collaboration platform with gamification aspects and other tools
12:30 – 13:30	Lunch Break
13:30 – 15:30	Demonstration of the project's applications and feedback collection (cont.): <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • AR training platform • Incident detection utilizing depth cameras • Incident detection utilizing thermal cameras, wearable devices and other tools • iDSS with Plant Data Exchange Component (PDEC)
15:30 – 16:30	Synergy with FACTS4WORKERS H2020 project: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Brief presentation of FACTS4WORKERS project • Discussion on potential synergy
16:30 – 16:45	Wrap-up and conclusions